

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Lopes, E. L., Mesquita, E., & Herrero, E. (2025). When stock disappears, psychology appears: The moderating effect of the regulatory focus on consumer reactions to out-of-stock. *Brazilian Administration Review*, 22(3), e240180. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-7692bar2025240180>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Lopes, E. L., Mesquita, E., Herrero, E., & Santini, F. O. (2025). Peer review report for: When stock disappears, psychology appears: The moderating effect of the regulatory focus on consumer reactions to out-of-stock. *Brazilian Administration Review*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16763763>

REVIEWERS:

- Fernando de Oliveira Santini (Universidade do Vale do Rio do Sinos, Brazil)
 - Sneha Pandey (Fortune Institute of International Business, India)
- The other reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.*

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Fernando de Oliveira Santini
Date review returned: November 25, 2024
Recommendation: Major revision

Comments to the authors

Dear Authors,

Thank you for the opportunity to review your manuscript titled “When Stock Disappears, Psychology Appears: The Moderating Effect of the Regulatory Focus on Consumer Reactions to Out-of-Stock.” Below, I provide my thoughts and suggestions:

Introduction

The introduction effectively presents the central idea of the article, which is commendable. However, the study's novelty is not sufficiently clear. What new insights or findings does this study provide that were not addressed in previous research?

Additionally, it would be beneficial to highlight the managerial contributions and relevance of this study. Including practical examples could help demonstrate how this phenomenon occurs in real-life scenarios.

Theoretical Section

The structure of the hypotheses feels inconsistent. Starting with complex hypotheses involving moderation, followed by direct relationships, seems counterintuitive. A clearer and more logical progression of hypotheses would improve this section.

It is unclear why eye-tracking was not used in all the studies. If visual attention is the primary dependent variable, consistency across experiments would strengthen the methodology.

Moderation Hypothesis

The moderation hypothesis requires further development. More robust theoretical explanations are necessary to substantiate the proposed relationships and make the hypotheses more convincing.

Experiment 1

It might be worth testing other extraneous variables, such as gender, age, and familiarity with milk purchasing, to assess their influence on the outcomes. Including these factors could enhance the study's rigor and insights.

Study 3

The sample size in Study 3 significantly compromises the validity of the results. A minimum of 30 respondents is typically required to ensure reliable analyses. Without an adequate sample size, the findings from this study cannot be considered robust.

Context Justification

The choice of contexts for each experiment needs further justification. Explaining why specific scenarios were chosen would add clarity and strengthen the methodological framework.

Results and Conclusion

The results and conclusions are overly descriptive, and the contributions appear too generic. The novelty of the study remains difficult to discern. Providing more detailed insights and specific contributions would help to clearly establish the study's value.

Thank you for considering my comments. I hope they assist you in refining and strengthening your manuscript.

Best regards,

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: No

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: No

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: No

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: No

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: none

Rating:

Interest: Average

Quality: Average

Originality: Below Average

Overall: Below Average

Authors' Response

Dear Professors Dr. Ricardo Limongi and Dr. Ruchi Gupta,

Editors of BAR,

We would like to start by expressing our gratitude for the attention given to our submission and for the thoughtful and constructive feedback provided by the three anonymous reviewers.

In this revised version, we have carefully addressed all the suggestions and comments, and we are confident that the article is now stronger and more competitive for consideration in BAR's esteemed editorial space.

That said, we remain fully open to any additional adjustments that might further enhance the article's relevance and appeal to the journal and its readership.

To streamline the review process, we have submitted two files for your convenience. The first file includes all changes highlighted using Word's track changes feature, while the second file presents a clean version with all adjustments incorporated for easier reading.

Thank you once again for this opportunity, and we look forward to hearing from you regarding the next steps.

Best regards,

The Authors

Adjustment suggestions - Reviewer 1

Introduction

The introduction effectively presents the central idea of the article, which is commendable. However, the study's novelty is not sufficiently clear. What new insights or findings does this study provide that were not addressed in previous research?

Additionally, it would be beneficial to highlight the managerial contributions and relevance of this study. Including practical examples could help demonstrate how this phenomenon occurs in real-life scenarios.

Author's response: Thank you for this recommendation. We will try to take this into account in the new version by adjusting the introduction of the paper.

This study builds on existing research by examining the psychological mechanisms underlying consumers' reactions to out-of-stock (OOS) situations, a problem for which no definitive solution yet exists (Che, Chen, & Chen, 2012). Previous studies have explored the effects of stockouts on consumer evaluations of retailers (Fitzsimons, 2000; He & Oppewal, 2018), behavioral intentions (Andaur, Ruz, & Goycoolea, 2021), shopping behavior and purchase decisions (Peterson, Kim, & Jeong, 2020), and recovery from service failures (Pizzi & Scarpi, 2013). Specifically, this study investigates how consumers' regulatory focus—promotion versus prevention—moderates purchase intentions in retail settings. This perspective offers novel insights by addressing a critical gap in the literature: the influence of individual psychological traits on consumer behavior during stockout situations. Understanding these dynamics enables retailers to design targeted strategies to mitigate negative reactions, such as dissatisfaction or store switching,

while fostering engagement and loyalty. Out-of-stock scenarios frequently occur in retail stores, and consumer responses to these situations vary both by the cause of the out-of-stock and the type of product affected. Research indicates that an out-of-stock product resulting from increased sales due to a store promotion has different effects on consumers compared to an out-of-stock of a regularly priced product (Kalantary et al., 2023). Previous studies also noted differences in consumer responses when an out-of-stock affects a targeted product (one on the consumer's shopping list) versus a non-targeted product (Lopes & Herrero, 2018). Despite the necessity of studying the origins and contexts of out-of-stock incidents (He & Oppewal, 2018), little has been explored regarding the influence of the consumer profile in this context. Consumers' perceptions of product availability in retail settings significantly impact purchasing intentions and behaviors, likely influenced by their personal, psychological, and emotional characteristics (Kumar, Sharma, & Tapar, 2021; Hoang, & Breugelmans, 2023). This study aims to fill this gap.

Regulatory focus is a personal trait that influences individuals' perceptions and motivations in judgment and decision-making processes (Higgins, 2012). According to this theory, individuals can be classified as having either a preventive or promotional regulatory focus. Promotional individuals are oriented toward achieving positive outcomes, focusing on gains or non-gains, whereas preventive individuals are motivated by the avoidance of losses or non-losses (Lichtenthaler, & Fischbach, 2019).

To investigate whether individual regulatory focus moderates consumers' purchase intentions in out-of-stock situations, we conducted three experimental studies. Each study was designed to explore specific aspects of this relationship: (1) the impact of regulatory focus on purchase intentions under different stock conditions; (2) the effects of manipulating regulatory focus on consumer behavior in stockout situations; and (3) the role of visual attention, measured through eye-tracking technology, in moderating these dynamics. These findings not only contribute to academic discourse but also provide practical insights for retail managers. For example, they suggest that targeted communication strategies, such as emphasizing restocking schedules for prevention-focused consumers or highlighting alternative promotions for promotion-focused consumers, can effectively address different customer needs.

Theoretical Section

The structure of the hypotheses feels inconsistent. Starting with complex hypotheses involving moderation, followed by direct relationships, seems counterintuitive. A clearer and more logical progression of hypotheses would improve this section.

It is unclear why eye-tracking was not used in all the studies. If visual attention is the primary dependent variable, consistency across experiments would strengthen the methodology.

Author's response: Thank you for your thoughtful comment. We would like to offer an alternative perspective. Given that hypotheses based on direct relationships are often not particularly novel, we aimed for parsimony in our study by avoiding the inclusion of hypotheses on direct relationships that may lack originality.

For this reason, our first hypothesis directly addresses a moderating effect, as psychological micromechanisms are widely recognized as the most revealing processes in scientific studies (see Padro, Korelo, and Da Silva, 2014).

While the second hypothesis is formulated based on a direct relationship, its purpose is to explain the effect observed in the first hypothesis. We believe that this ordering contributes to a more coherent and fluid reading of the study. Although it would be relatively simple to rearrange the hypotheses as suggested, we feel it is worth presenting our reasoning to the reviewer for further reflection and consideration. Thank you again for your feedback, and we remain open to any additional comments or suggestions.

Moderation Hypothesis

The moderation hypothesis requires further development. More robust theoretical explanations are necessary to substantiate the proposed relationships and make the hypotheses more convincing.

Author's response: As a way of complying with the recommendation, we sought to provide a greater theoretical basis for the mediation hypothesis.

Regulatory focus theory (Higgins, 1997, 2012) differentiates individuals into two main profiles: promotion focus and prevention focus. While promotion focus is associated with the pursuit of gains and positive outcomes, prevention

focus is linked to the avoidance of losses and the minimization of risks (Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2019). These distinct orientations influence how consumers process information and make decisions in retail environments.

Prevention-focused individuals are more vigilant and attentive to signs of potential failures or threats in their surroundings (Lee & Aaker, 2004). In out-of-stock contexts, such as empty shelves, these consumers may perceive unavailability as an indicator of risk or a problem, which tends to intensify negative reactions and lower their purchase intentions.

Conversely, promotion-focused consumers have a goal-oriented mindset, interpreting adversities as opportunities. In out-of-stock situations, they may demonstrate greater resilience, exploring available alternatives and maintaining their purchase intentions (Förster & Higgins, 2005; Hüttermann & Memmert, 2015). These distinct behaviors suggest that regulatory focus moderates consumers' reactions to product unavailability.

Experiment 1

It might be worth testing other extraneous variables, such as gender, age, and familiarity with milk purchasing, to assess their influence on the outcomes. Including these factors could enhance the study's rigor and insights.

Author's response: Thank you for this suggestion. After analysis, we identified that there were no significant effects for the demographic variables. We have included this perspective in the new version.

Although there were no theoretical assumptions suggesting possible effects between demographic variables and the dependent variable, we analyzed the relationship of age ($r = 0.001$; $p > 0.10$), education ($Z = 2.060$), and gender ($M_{\text{men}} = 3.96$; $M_{\text{women}} = 4.01$; $t(158) = 0.234$; $p > 0.10$) on purchase intention, with no significant effects found

Study 3

The sample size in Study 3 significantly compromises the validity of the results. A minimum of 30 respondents is typically required to ensure reliable analyses. Without an adequate sample size, the findings from this study cannot be considered robust.

Author's response: We recognized this major limit in our study. Because of this, we completed the collection with a total of 65 participants. As expected, the results were consistent with the initial sample, but the significance of the tests was enhanced. The new indicators are reported in this new version.

Context Justification

The choice of contexts for each experiment needs further justification. Explaining why specific scenarios were chosen would add clarity and strengthen the methodological framework.

Author's response: Thank you for your recommendation. In the new version, we have included the justification for the choice of contexts and experimental stimuli in each of the three studies.

The scenario chosen for Experiment 1—the purchase of milk in a supermarket—was selected for its practical relevance and broad applicability. Basic necessity products, such as milk, are highly likely to appear on consumers' shopping lists, making them an appropriate choice for exploring reactions to out-of-stock situations (Huang & Zhang, 2016). Additionally, the target audience's familiarity with this type of purchase minimizes behavioral variations associated with a lack of knowledge or prior experience, enabling a more accurate analysis of the effects of regulatory focus.

In Experiment 2, the choice of light bulbs as the target product reflects an attempt to explore a context distinct from the first experiment. Products like light bulbs, though less common in regular purchases, represent items of situational necessity that, when unavailable, may cause greater frustration for consumers (Ozuem et al., 2017). This variation in product type allows for an investigation of whether the effects of regulatory focus are consistent across different purchasing scenarios, contributing to a broader understanding of the phenomenon under study.

For Study 3, we used a virtual shelf of cookies. Products like cookies are often purchased impulsively (Streicher et al., 2021), making them ideal for investigating how consumers with different regulatory profiles allocate visual attention

to shelves with stockouts. Using a scenario involving lower-value, unplanned purchases helps test the generalizability of the findings in contexts with lower financial commitment.

Results and Conclusion

The results and conclusions are overly descriptive, and the contributions appear too generic. The novelty of the study remains difficult to discern. Providing more detailed insights and specific contributions would help to clearly establish the study's value.

Author's response: Thank you for your recommendation. In this new version of the text, we have tried to reduce the descriptive perspective of the discussions of the findings and, both in the individual studies and in the general discussion, we will try to be more propositional with theoretical and managerial implications.

Thank you for considering my comments. I hope they assist you in refining and strengthening your manuscript.

Author's response: it is we who thank you for your detailed reading and great recommendations. Thank you very much!

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 2 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 2 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

Reviewer 3 report

Reviewer: Sneha Pandey

Date review returned: November 17, 2024

Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

I personally enjoyed reading the research paper. However, a few suggestions for the authors:

1. On Page 4, a two line conclusion must be avoided and merged with the paragraph above.
2. An introductory paragraph for 'Method' should not be a single line (page 6).
3. On page 10, in study 2- please see if the first two paragraphs can be merged.
4. Similarly, on page 15, in Study 3- a single sentence can't be considered as a separate paragraph. The authors can combine the two lines to form a single paragraph.
5. The Discussions and Conclusion section is very well-written.

The paper does:

1. contribute to theory and practice in the field of business or public administration
2. address advancements to the frontiers of scholarly knowledge and organizational practice on a global scale instead of providing insights to a particular country or region

3. include bibliographical references made up of (almost only) up-to-date articles published in reputed scholarly journals available in English
4. make reference to classic authors and current developments on the theories mentioned in the paper
5. clearly state a compelling research question and the conceptual model.
6. describe in due methodological detail.
9. be skillfully crafted to properly address the conceptual model and answer the research question
10. be thoroughly checked for scholarly and English writing.

Kindly also check if all the in-text citations have been mentioned in the reference section.

Good luck with the paper.

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: none

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Excellent

Originality: Excellent

Overall: Excellent

Authors' Response

Adjustment suggestions - Reviewer 3

1. On Page 4, a two line conclusion must be avoided and merged with the paragraph above.

Author's response: Thanks to the reviewer. The request has been fulfilled in the new version.

2. An introductory paragraph for 'Method' should not be a single line (page 6).

Author's response: Thanks to the reviewer. The request has been fulfilled in the new version.

3. On page 10, in study 2- please see if the first two paragraphs can be merged.

Author's response: Thanks to the reviewer. The request has been fulfilled in the new version.

4. Similarly, on page 15, in Study 3- a single sentence can't be considered as a separate paragraph. The authors can combine the two lines to form a single paragraph.

Author's response: Thanks to the reviewer. The request has been fulfilled in the new version.

Open Peer Review Report _____

5. The Discussions and Conclusion section is very well-written.

Author's response: Thank you for recognizing our efforts.

6. Kindly ensure that the paper does:

a. contribute to theory and practice in the field of business or public administration

b. address advancements to the frontiers of scholarly knowledge and organizational practice on a global scale instead of providing insights to a particular country or region

c. include bibliographical references made up of (almost only) up-to-date articles published in reputed scholarly journals available in English

d. make reference to classic authors and current developments on the theories mentioned in the paper

e. clearly state a compelling research question and the conceptual model.

f. describe in due methodological detail.

g. be skillfully crafted to properly address the conceptual model and answer the research question

Author's response: Revised manuscript.

h. be thoroughly checked for scholarly and English writing.

Author's response: Thanks to the reviewer. We would like to thank the reviewer. A detailed review has been carried out on the new version in order to ensure that all the points indicated have been met.

7. Kindly also check if all the in-text citations have been mentioned in the reference section.

Author's response: Thanks. Revised.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Fernando de Oliveira Santini

Date review returned: March 03, 2025

Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the authors

The authors did a great job in their revision. Congratulations!

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable): none

Rating:

Interest: Good

Quality: Good

Originality: Good

Overall: Good

Authors' Response

There was no reviewer's evaluation for this round. For this reason, there is no authors' response.